

Teräs, M. & Moreno-Herrero, L. (2019). Using digital devices for learning vocational expertise in high- and low-technology contexts – Case studies in Finnish and & Cuban contexts. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.56-66) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2651250>

Using digital devices for learning vocational expertise in high- and low-technology contexts – Case studies in Finnish and & Cuban contexts

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Abstract

Digital competence is an important ability for humanity in the 21st century. The use of technological tools in VET schools has expanded in recent years. Digital technologies cover a wide variety of tools such as computers, robots, learning environments, digital media like blogs, wikis and social media. The aim of the paper is to present for discussion uses of technological tools such as simulations in both high-technology context like Finland and in low-technology context like Cuba. Technologies can act as a means for inclusion and exclusion to communities in multiple levels: in classrooms, organizations, work places as well as countries. The paper reflects on how the use of technological tools promotes learning vocations and what kinds of challenges do exist with digitalization. Furthermore, we discuss how the use of technological tools changes practices of VET.

Keywords

simulations; digital technology; technology for learning

1. Introduction

The use of technological tools in schools has expanded in recent years; even though such tools have existed already decades. Digital technologies cover a wide variety of tools such as computers, robots, learning environments, digital media like blogs, wikis and social media. In this paper, we will focus on uses of simulations in learning vocations. The aim of the paper is to discuss and reflect on uses of these technological tools in both high-technology contexts like Finland and in low-technology context like Cuba. Digital technologies can act as a means for inclusion and exclusion to communities in multiple levels: in classrooms, organizations, work places as well as countries. Digital divide is the concept that describes inequalities in access to digital technologies and Internet as well as inequalities in skills and how it is used (cf. Rogers, 2016).

The paper reflects on how the use of technological tools promotes learning vocations and what kinds of challenges do exist with digitalization. In the paper we investigate across national and technological boundaries to discuss the challenges that emerge in accordance to stage of technology development. Likewise, challenges for teachers and organization of the learning process are examined and discussed.

Hakkarainen (2009) pointed out how use of technology-mediated learning changes also knowledge-practices. He concluded that technology enhances learning through transformed social practices. In other words, not the use of technological tools as such, but how techno-

logical tools are integrated as part of teachers' and students' social practices. In VET, also how technological tools are part of vocational and professional practices.

The Finnish case explores simulations in the health care field. Gaba (2011) has outlined that simulations are perceived as attempts to replicate a clinical situation to amplify or replace actual experience. Simulations are divided into three categories—live, virtual, and constructive simulations—involving live people, simulators, and simulated systems, such as gaming with avatars (Sokolowski, 2011). Challenges in health care area are, as Poikela and Teräs (2015) pointed out in their review, that pedagogical knowledge was often thin.

The Cuban case has a special challenge in how to deal with scarcity of resources and develop alternatives ways that permit access to advantages of digital technologies. Here initiatives and creativity in using learning environments becomes essential.

The VET system in Cuba is expected to meet work market's needs, and at the same time, VET is given an important role in social inclusion. A main challenge for the VET system, in particular since 1990s and up to day, is how to meet technological development internationally given the graduate access to knowledge of these technologies, and at the same time, satisfying local needs that are often not related to highly developed devices.

The paper concerns the following three research questions:

- What are the challenges and benefits of simulations experienced by teachers and students in health care in Finland?
- What are the main features of the use technologies for learning in cuba's VET system as depicted in research?
- What are the challenges and benefits of using technologies for learning in low-tech and high-tech contexts?

2. The Finnish case: Challenges and benefits of simulations

Simulation training is historically rooted in aviation and military education, areas that have also been studied for ideas by health care practitioners and educators, which are the main focus of this research (Gaba, 2012). An international expert meeting (Issenberg, Ringsted, Ostergaard, & Dieckmann, 2011) identified three areas in which new knowledge concerning health care simulations was urgently needed: instructional design, outcomes measurement, and translational research. This research addresses the first area by asking what kinds of pedagogical challenges are faced in simulations.

Simulation training is frequently divided into three phases: briefing of the situation, the simulation event itself (called a scenario), and debriefing of the simulation event (Dieckmann, 2009). These phases are used to organise training in practice. Problems may arise if learning is conceived as this linear process model suggests, because learning is a dynamic process and is part of all phases. Furthermore, we know that, for example, motivation, perception and learning environment have effect on learning.

Sokolowski's (2011) three modes of simulations are found in different vocational domains: live, simulators, and computer-based modes. However, in the health care domain, traditional tools, such as anatomical models, are merged into new technologies to form high-fidelity patient simulators that are frequently used to learn nursing practices, such as resuscitation after a heart attack.

2.1 The study

Simulations are used to learn and develop high-level skills and knowledge needed in specific domains, like caring for a trauma patient (Rosqvist & Lauritsalo, 2013). They are found to be beneficial in learning nursing practices, especially clinical skills and bridging classroom and clinical learning (Darcy Mahoney et al., 2013) and so called non-technical skills such as communication, decision-making, leadership and team work (Jankouskas et al., 2007). Cant and Cooper (2010) reviewed 12 studies and found out that six had demonstrated positive effects on learning (e.g., gaining knowledge and self-confidence and learning critical thinking) whereas six studies did not show effects. There are also challenges identified in simulation literature such as economic and personnel resources required in implementing simulations. Berragan (2011) further pointed out concerns about what are real capacities of simulations to translate to practices and how quick development of technology might take a leading role in learning nursing practices. Furthermore, Langemeyer (2012) aptly pointed out that students can also learn stereotypical professional and gender roles in simulations.

Previous research focusing on simulations in health care has employed different theories as a springboard to explain learning. Studies have employed constructivism, behaviourism, or a combination of both (Parker & Myrick, 2009), experiential learning, expert learning (Nehring & Lashley, 2009), problem-based learning (Poikela, 2012), and social practices (Dieckmann, 2009). Poikela and Teräs (2015) found in their scoping review 13 different conceptualizations of learning in nursing simulations and five different pedagogical models. Furthermore, researchers had employed both educational theories and theories from other disciplines such as critical feminist theory or social sciences.

In the Finnish context, simulations have been studied in educational areas, especially military medicine and mass casualty situations (Jokela, 2010) and forest machine training (Salakari, 2007); health care areas (Poikela, 2012); in the philosophy of science and technology work (Mattila, 2006); and construction industry work (Kerosuo et al., 2012).

2.2 Method and analysis

The study is part of the larger research called “Developing and learning expertise via simulations”.¹ The aim of the study was to examine how students and teachers perceived simulation training. Participants were 16 nursing students and 9 teachers. The teachers (out of 13) answered a qualitative electronic questionnaire involving 12 open-ended questions. 16 students (out of 19) answered similar type of questionnaire from students’ perspective. The participants studied and worked in the Finnish Universities of Applied Sciences. Data were collected in 2013-2014. The focus of this presentation is on the qualitative questionnaire data.

Before the study started, research permits were applied from the Institutes and the consent was asked from the participants. The questions for teachers involved background information such as teaching subjects, years in teaching the profession, work life experiences and five questions about simulations: How does simulation method differ from other teaching methods, what kinds of issues promote learning in simulations, what kinds of issues hinder learning in simulations, what kinds of issues are beneficial to teach in simulations, and what kinds of issues are not beneficial to teach in simulations? The questions for the students involved three background questions such as the starting year of the studies and if they had participated in simulations, and four questions about simulations: How do simulations differ from other studying methods, what kinds of issues promote studying in simulations, what

¹ Previously the Finnish case was presented in World TVET Conference in Malaysia 2015

kinds of issues hinder studying in simulations, and what kinds of issues are beneficial to study in simulations?

Analysis followed a qualitative thematic analysis and its six phases: familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and producing the report (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Analysis was conducted with Atlas.ti the software program. Answers to questions were short sentences involving one or more issues the participants wanted to bring forward about teaching, studying and learning in simulations.

Initially 20 different codes were identified in students' responses such as simulating authentic work situation and practical skills. In teachers' responses 34 different codes were identified such as working practices, teachers' competence and inspiring experiences. Thus, teachers identified more issues than students about the strengths and challenges of simulations. However, when searching for themes four themes were identified in the responses of both groups: 1) differences 2) usefulness 3) conduciveness, and 4) challenges. Theme usefulness and conduciveness were categorized as strengths and theme challenge and differences were reported as such. I will next give the examples of the themes according to research questions: How do simulations differ from other teaching and studying methods? What kinds of strengths and challenges do teachers and students identify in simulations?

2.3 Results

15 students had started their studies in 2012 and one in 2010. All were nursing students and they had participated in simulations during their training. Six teachers taught nursing and three management and services. Seven teachers had taught in simulations and two had not.

Differences

Both students and teachers recognized differences. They both compared it with reading a book and thought that it was a "better way to study than reading a book" (S8²) as one of the students put it. In addition teachers thought that simulation method was intensive and comprehensive and that "one needs to throw oneself in a different way, one can really experiment and also fail" (T7).

2.4 Strengths

Both students and teachers thought that usefulness of simulations was especially in "learning working practices" (T1). One of the students responded that simulations are useful in "especially practicing such situations, which are rare in real nursing work" (S5). Both identified that simulations are good at linking theory to practice, learning group work and collaboration and learning from mistakes.

The students highlighted authenticity that simulations "help to prepare oneself for real patient situation" (S3) as well as learning practical skills such as "nursing procedures" (S11). Furthermore, students wrote that "practicing demanding procedures before internships gives self-confidence" (S6), and simulations are useful when one can see her/his own performance. Students also favored that "you learn more when you are doing things" (S2).

The teachers brought out that simulations are also useful in professional development and that it can be used all kinds of teaching as one of the teachers put it: "Simulation is flexible and it can be used for many kinds of teaching, one can apply it to all." (T9).

² S=student, T=teacher, numbers refer to individual participants.

Both students and teachers responded to that better organization of simulations can promote learning: "Simulation days are long, often between 8-16, towards the end one gets too tired and focus loosens. Also one has to always wait for one's own turn." (S8). The teacher also thought about integration: "Even more exact integration into the curriculum and different learning objectives." (T8). The students wished for more simulations and smaller groups, and the teachers more resources and support from the management. In addition teachers recognized that they needed more competence about teaching in simulations: "Developing staff's competence."(T4).

2.5 Challenges

When considering the challenges, the respondents' answers differed. The students brought out six issues and the teachers five. The students highlighted the artificiality of simulations: "I see simulation situations unnatural from time to time."(S4), and feeling of tension: "For a worrier it can be painful." (S10). They also presented that follow-up was inconvenient: It would promote learning "if they would not be videotaped" (S14), as well as lack of instruments. One student thought that the whole activity was in vain: "I think that studying in simulations is stupid and therefore it should be stopped." (S13).

The teachers highlighted as a challenge "lack of competence." (T4) and problems with implementation: "Too difficult cases, technology is not working." (T9). They also identified personnel and economic resources as challenges. Furthermore, they brought out the size of a student group and knowing working life: "Lack of clinical skills." (T5).

The teachers presented six situations in which they would not use simulations as a teaching method: "Teaching theoretical issues." (T1), processing student's personal life, recognizing previous competence, teaching issues related to death, research work, and "those issues that can be learned later in working life, and are low risk tasks if one fails"(T4).

3. The Cuban case: Challenges and benefits of using technology to support learning

The use of technology in the classroom has an important impact and to great extent shapes educational practices (Cuban, Kirpatrick & Peck, 2001). Cuban educational system, including VET, performs better than most countries of the region regardless of limitations (Fleites, 2013). The use of technology to support learning has been much in focus in the Cuban VET system, a system that has largely been schools based despite strong connection with work place secured by a very centralised governance of education (Gasparini, 2000).

3.1 Research material

This study is driven by an interest in investigating how technology to support learning has been used in the context of a low technology developed country (Cuba) that shows considerable success in educating work forces. The study is limited in scope. It essentially aims to provide initial grounds for deeper and broader analysis of the use of technology for learning within the VET system in Cuba.

In a literature search, including review of data bases in Cuba, it was noticeable that research in this area is scarce if not largely missing. There is however a valuable piece of research that arguably sets grounds for further studies about the use of educational technology in Cuban VET system. Najia Sabir and Anne Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014) from Indiana University, studied empirically how VET institutions, or polytechnic high schools as termed in their study, prepare students for labour market using technological tools. The empirical part of their study is largely referred in this article.

Focusing on the Cuban educational system Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 250) refer to earlier research to argue that educational guidelines and trends illuminate how school-

ing mechanisms have been shaped to accommodate economic, political and social needs. Additionally, they argue, that it is important to evaluate the perspectives of teachers as they relate to leveraging technology in instruction. Without a clear understanding of teacher values and perspectives, interventions will not be as successful. From this, a clear understanding of context is invaluable.

The post-revolution Cuban educational systems is primarily a state-controlled, centralized system that is responsible for the development of society and educator perspectives. According to Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 250) these educational policies and top-down approaches have impacted teacher perceptions on how to prepare Cuban citizens. Over time, school-level administrators and teachers have adopted this centralized vision of educating students, in an effort to better meet productivity goals. The study suggest the relevance to first understand their value systems of teachers.

3.2 Results

Using Erikson's data analysis techniques Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 258) developed assertions of how Cuban polytechnic teachers perceived and used educational technology. Based on the questionnaires and interviews, teachers reported highly valuing their technical pedagogical training, indicating that the growing spaces were an integral part of their technology based instruction. According to this study limited resources was the greatest barrier to the implementation of educational technology. The following assertions emerged in the study. The teachers perceived that educational technology met a wide variety of teaching and learning purposes; technology allowed them to extend the classroom; more resources would enhance their teaching; and polytechnic education was reported as a valuable experience for students. Likewise the study found that teacher perspectives in this school were greatly shaped by the lack of advanced technology available.

The four main finding of the study (Sabir & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2014, pp. 258-261) are presented in the following.

First, educational technology is viewed as inclusive of any technological devices that prepare students for their future careers, even in labor.

During the observation and on-site interviews done by Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 258), when teachers described educational technology, they mentioned a wide range of devices that would help prepare students for their future careers. For example, when asked about educational technology during an onsite interview, one teacher discussed the importance of greenhouses and how this particular technology enabled students educational experiences of differentiating between vegetation and knowing how to care for the variety of foliage. Although greenhouses would not typically fall under traditional definitions of educational technology focusing heavily on digital technologies, teachers here seemed to express broader definitions of educational technology devices and tools that could benefit their students.

Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 258) report that during the interview and site observations, teachers explained that the wide fields and greenhouses were representative of learning spaces. The principal explained plants were grown, labelled, and tended for by the students, in short, some greenhouses were "complete student initiatives." During the teacher interviews, the greenhouses and other outdoor learning spaces were referenced as instructional tools that teach students the crucial skills of: identifying different types of plants; their uses and how to care for them.

Second, technology is used to extend the classroom from traditional spaces into the outdoors to accomplish meaningful student learning.

During the site observation Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 259) found out that the teachers pointed out aspects of different types of technology the school incorporates in

their lessons and classrooms. They report that during one of these exchanges, a teacher humorously points to two oxen tied to short coconut trees near a classroom door, claiming the pair as education and assistive tools. While meant as a humorous comment, the principal was quick to jump in the conversation to point out the importance of the animals to the school and the students' learning, referring to them as "tools."

This introduction of ICT tools is important in establishing the definition of educational technologies for the purpose of expanding traditional learning spaces into the outdoors. Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 259) reports that while touring additional greenhouses and outdoor spaces a teacher refers to these as "important classrooms," where students learn to tend to animals and vegetation. For example during the interviews, the teachers comment that students must not only learn how to distinguish between the types of plants, determining their properties and value, but be able to care for them appropriately, everything from planting a seed to caring for a full grown tree.

Typically, a black tarp-like canopy encompasses the plots of land creating a roof-like structure, and cascading down slightly on all four sides. Teachers, during the observation, describe this as an important 'technological' aspect. In that the 'canopy' provides more than shade and the students learn how to create structures and appropriately alter the amount of sunlight the plants receive. Students must learn the functions of many of their outside classrooms. Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 259) describe that the teacher was quick to call this structure as technology of the classroom that facilitated student learning. Furthermore this was seen an extension of the classroom from the physical bounds of the brick-and-mortar classrooms. This type of learning takes the students outdoors into a real-world context where they have to master appropriate skills.

The study by Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 259) describes that several black tarped greenhouses introduced as learning spaces, where students learn through practice. For example, one unique feature pointed out is a water trench that students need to walk through to get into the learning space. A teacher explains how the students have to ensure sanitation and healthy plants. The teacher describes how the students need to learn how to naturally keep away pests and bugs that would harm their cultivations. The teacher says that the students 'have to clean their shoes' before and after coming out of the greenhouse, she is careful to place emphasis on the students' learning throughout the process of entering this particular classroom.

During the on-site interview conducted by Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 259), principal displayed a wildlife area of the school explaining that the school is a 'polytechnic agricultural school' that teaches more than how to 'grow plants'. The students also learn how to 'care for livestock' at this school. For example, during the site observation, a teacher highlights an elevated livestock facility pointing out a very large pig housed in a pen, situated next to the large animal is a litter of piglets. The teacher describes how the students learn to take care of the animal, they learn how to 'breed, feed and tend' for it. The principal highlights the pig pen, in an interview: the pen houses very large pig surrounded by several of its smaller piglets. The large pig is isolated between steel bars. The principal describes how the mother pig would roll over her babies and claimed this was an issue for the school. In response to this need the school imported, from Japan, this bit of teaching technology, which was considered a 'new advancement'. The purpose of integrating this tool was to 'teach the students how to care for livestock' in an appropriate and humane manner. Furthermore, the authors report that the principal referred to the technology of the pen as key in the teaching process. Additional learning spaces, including chicken coops, fodder houses, and other livestock holding areas were also toured as learning spaces.

Third, the teachers believed that their instruction could be enhanced with better access to technological teaching materials and their training was vital to their development.

During the interviews conducted by Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 260) with university faculty the aspect of equal resource distribution and teacher preparation was a key focus. Due to national policies all traditional classrooms had equal and standard allocations of resources. With the national requirement for teacher preparation, 80% of the teachers reported being 'well prepared' to use educational technology in their classroom, 10% felt 'somewhat prepared,' and the other 10% felt 'very well prepared'. Most of the teachers surveyed had been teaching for at least 6 years, with only a handful having taught less than 3 years. Additionally, several teachers mentioned courses, in recycling for example (n=5/9), that shaped their use of educational technologies.

When asked in the study (Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2014, p. 260) about their comfort level in terms of using technology in their classrooms in the questionnaire, there were four options: very comfortable, comfortable, somewhat comfortable, and not comfortable. While 80% percent of the teachers said that they felt 'comfortable using technology' in their classroom, only 5% said that they were 'not very comfortable.' In the questionnaire, when teachers were asked about how often they used technology, 55% of teachers reported that they used technology between 5-10 times a week, while 30% of the teachers said that they used technology at least 11-15 times a week. Teachers defined these activities as instructional material integration, lesson planning, classroom activities, classroom management, or communication with colleagues. Half of the 22 teachers assigned homework that required a computer once or twice a week, while four teachers reported assigning more computer-based homework more than three times a week. However, none of the teachers noted using technology for administrative purposes, such as attendance, or analyzing student performance, such as identifying student performance trends through a grade book. Only one respondent reported using technology to communicate with peers or students. While only 15% claimed to actively use electronic resources, it is important to note that their definitions of educational technology resources tended to include greenhouses and other technologies that were not electronically based.

Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 260) report also the very limited access to the Internet; specifically, teachers did have access to an Intranet which contained CD-based information. While this point was brought up during several teacher interviews, the university faculty and even translators confirmed the limited access to the World Wide Web. In the interviews the university faculty explained the concept of the intranet. The intranet housed resources, such as instructional videos, simulations, and digital lesson plans, which were distributed to all the regions. These recourses were normally delivered directly to the school site and housed on-site.

Fourth, polytechnic education is viewed as valuable in creating productive and technical students, as defined by teachers and faculty.

According the outcomes of the questionnaire used by the authors of the study (Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2014, p. 260) a majority, 85% of respondents, mentioned that they used technological tools to facilitate high order thinking in their classrooms. During the observation, teachers described their high-order thinking activities as teachers expanding the classroom outdoors and had students solve problems in real-world contexts. 95% of the teachers use technology for personal productivity, using word processors to create worksheets and tests in their school computer labs. Lastly all of the teachers reported using technology to present information and to facilitate specific learning concepts.

Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p. 261) report that another important practice-based teaching experience is the use of cigar presses as instructional technology. During the study, one of the classrooms observed is purposed specifically for the teaching of this process. The classroom is filled with tiny wooden desks, at first glance it seems difficult that high school students would even be able to sit at these desks, let alone two students to a table. In the cor-

ner of the room were large sticks, and piles of leaves covered with fabric. A teacher explains that this is the 'drying room' where students learn to cultivate, harvest and produce tobacco. The students bring the leaves into this room to study and press and roll them into cigars. The desks actually hold single presses, cigar pressers for the tobacco leaves. As the teacher describes how the classroom is actually used and the mechanisms by which the students use the press technology, she describes this with such pride claiming this classroom as an important aspect of helping Cuba become a global contender by increasing its exports. According to the study the students in this school are one of the region's largest cigar producers, as identified by the principal. When the teacher describes the students using the technology of the cigar press she discusses this in the context of her students helping the entire nation from an economic developmental perspective.

4. Summary and conclusions

This paper presented two different studies focusing on use of digital devices to learn vocations. The Finnish case examined one specific case: use of simulations to learn nursing practices, and the Cuban case was an overview of using technology in education. The first study was conducted in a high-technology context and the second one in low-technology context. Both studies show that use of digital devices has increased in both contexts to learn vocations, which poses both opportunities and challenges for the students and teachers in VET.

The results of the study, in the Finnish case, showed that the students and teachers agreed that learning in simulations was beneficial. They thought that simulations were useful especially learning practical skills needed at workplaces such as nursing procedures. Both acknowledged that simulations are good at linking theory to practice, learning group work and collaboration. Both also thought that better organization, implementation and integration would promote learning in nursing simulations. These results are in congruence with previous studies done in nursing simulations (cf. Cant & Cooper, 2010).

The participants' perceptions differed on challenges. The students identified as the biggest challenges that simulation was an unnatural situation and that some students felt tension when participating into simulations. Whereas the teachers recognized as the biggest challenges lack of competence and resources simulation demanded, both human and economic resources. This result shows that both groups approached challenges from their individual and situational points of view. In relation to challenges both students and teachers were on their zone of uncomfortable.

From practical points of view, the results provoke four issues. First, what can be done in relations to promoting the authenticity of simulations, the situational factor, and second, how to relieve students' tension. Third, how to develop teachers' competences for teaching in simulations, and fourth, how to ensure sufficient resources.

Responding to the first and second issues, two measures can be suggested. These are both intertwined to the third one, a competent teacher who knows working life as well as pedagogical principles can both create authentic simulations and relieve students' tension. The fourth one is a question for the management of institutes. If the management supports using the simulation method, sufficient resources need to be allocated.

The simulation method has become popular in health care training. The results of this study showed that it has both strengths and challenges. Each institute that uses the method, needs to solve these challenges according to their local circumstances and listening to their students and teachers.

As for the Cuban case, according to the findings in the study by Sabir and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2014, p.261), which are supported by other studies (c.f. Wang & Woo, 2007; Cuban, Kirkpatrick & Peck, 2001), while differing from traditional definition of technology, the teachers expanded their notion of technological education tools. The traditional definition of

ICT, explained as it is simply a “tool” in the education context is much contested by the findings of the study. This leaves then then space for a more comprehensive definition of educational technology as the creation, use and management of appropriate technological processes and resources. The teachers in this case study expanded their definition of educational technologies to include for example greenhouses and outdoor learning spaces. According to the study teachers viewed the construct of technology to be: inclusive of all technological resources available for instructional purpose, and a useful tool in moving learning from physical classrooms into real-world spaces. Teachers integrated tools they believed were relevant to their instructional context and governed by the Cuban educational system’s values.

Both studies showed that using technology changes practices of VET, which means that digital competences are needed. This article is just an initial step for intended comparative of contrasting contexts that is considered of paramount relevance for research in VET.

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